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Accidental Spreading of ^{90}Sr from the Ob and Yenisey Rivers under Global Warming

by

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Abstract

The spatial and temporal distributions of the anthropogenic radionuclides ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr , originating from nuclear bomb testing, the Sellafield reprocessing plants in the Irish Sea, and the Ob and Yenisey river discharges, have been simulated using the Nansen Center global version of the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM). The physical model is forced with daily atmospheric re-analyses fields for the period 1950 to present. Comparison of the temporal evolution of the observed and the simulated concentrations of ^{137}Cs have been conducted for the regions east of Scotland, west of central Norway, and at the entrance of the Barents Sea. Comparison of the temporal evolution of the observed and the simulated concentrations of ^{90}Sr have also been performed in the Kara Sea. It is shown that the radionuclides from the Sellafield discharge reach the Barents Sea region after 4-5 years, in accordance with observations. The simulation provides a detailed distribution and evolution of the radionuclides over the integration time. For the Atlantic waters off the coast of Norway and in the southern Barents Sea, the atmospheric fallout dominates over the Sellafield release up to the mid 1960s and from the early 1990s, whereas Sellafield is the main source for the two radionuclides in the 1970s and 1980s. The Ob river discharge dominates the surface ^{90}Sr over most of the Arctic Ocean and along the eastern and western coasts of Greenland before 1960. During the period of 1980 to 1990, the atmospheric fallout and the Ob river discharge are equally important for the ^{90}Sr distribution in the Arctic Ocean. The difference between present-day and the $2\times\text{CO}_2$ warming scenario runs for accidental releases of ^{90}Sr in the Ob and Yenisey rivers indicates that the transport of the tracers can be accelerated in the $2\times\text{CO}_2$ warming scenario run. It also follows that more of the released ^{90}Sr is confined to the Arctic Ocean in the global warming run, particularly in the near coastal, non-European part of the Arctic Ocean. Therefore, a global warming scenario may change the surface circulation more than the natural variability of the system at present-day forcing.

1 Background

Radioactive contamination of the Arctic environment has received increasing authoritative, scientific and public awareness over the last 10-15 years. This is caused by the fact that there are many actual and potential sources of radioactive sources within and near the Arctic region, and that the Arctic food chains are particularly vulnerable to radioactive exposure.

Optimal quantification of the temporal-spatial distribution of the radionuclides can only be achieved by bridging accurate time histories (or source functions) of the radionuclides, available *in situ* observations (possibly in combination with an improved monitoring strategy), and 3-dimensional simulation by state-of-the-art Ocean General Circulation Models (OGCMs).

Furthermore, ocean currents and mixing processes govern the transport of all conservative substances in the ocean. As the global climate system changes as a result of increasing concentration of radiatively active gasses and particles in the atmosphere, the dynamics and the thermodynamics of the ocean will also change. The change in the ocean climate will have consequences for the transport and mixing of radionuclides in the Atlantic-Arctic region. To assess spreading and mixing characteristics of radionuclides under a global warming scenario, an evaluated and validated model system needs to be used.

The objectives of the presented work are threefold:

- to assess the skill by which the Nansen Center version of MICOM can simulate the spreading and mixing of ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr at the high northern latitudes for the time period 1950 to present;
- to quantify the time history and contributions from different sources; and
- to predict a possible pathway of accidentally released radioactivity under a global warming scenario.

2 Introduction

A scientifically based description, understanding, quantification and potential prediction of the spatial distribution, temporal evolution and biogeochemical consequences of human-generated contamination of the environment require integrated use of observations and numerical modeling. Here a 3-dimensional OGCM is used to demonstrate the usefulness, and also to point towards the limitations, of simulating pathways and levels of trace compounds in the ocean environment. The trace compounds used in the study are the anthropogenic radionuclides ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr originating from nuclear bomb testing, the Sellafield release to the Irish Sea, and transported with the Ob and Yenisey rivers to the Arctic Ocean. Only ^{137}Cs has been used for the Yenisey river, yielding a total of seven tracers for the present day climate forcing. The Chernobyl release in 1986 is not included in the present study.

The model system used in this work has been validated against observed chlorofluorocarbon (CCl_3F and CCl_2F_2) distributions in the North Atlantic Ocean for the period 1931 to present (Gao et al., 2003a), focussing on multi-annual to decadal scale ventilation and water mass transformation processes in the region. In addition, mass transports in and out of the Nordic Seas region have been validated based on observations and observational-based estimates for the last 50 years (Nilsen et al., 2003). Both studies show that the model system is

able to describe most of the key observed quantities in a fairly realistic manner. It is therefore believed that the model system is a potentially useful tool in simulating the advective transport and dispersive mixing of radionuclides which behave conservatively in sea water.

There are a few examples that OGCMs have been used to simulate the temporal and spatial distributions of man-made radionuclides (e.g. Gao et al. 2003b; Gerland et al. 2003; Tsumune et al. 2003; Nies et al. 1998). In these works, Tsumune et al. (2003) performed a global simulation of ^{137}Cs and $^{239,240}\text{Pu}$ concentrations with the source from the atmospheric fallout, and Gerland et al. (2003) performed a regional simulation of ^{99}Tc with the source from the Sellafield reprocessing plant.

The present simulation differs from the large scale OGCM simulation by Nies et al. (1998) in the following ways: A fully on-line instead of off-line integration procedure is adopted; the model is forced with synoptic (i.e., daily) atmospheric fields instead of climatological (i.e., monthly mean) forcing fields; a truly global OGCM with a horizontally stretched grid system is used instead of a regional North Atlantic-Arctic model set-up; both atmospheric fallout, the Sellafield discharge and input from the Yenisey and Ob rivers are simulated in contrast to the Sellafield release only; and the integration time period is 1950–1999 compared to 1965–1995.

The report is organized as follows: A description of the model system is provided in Section 3. The radionuclides simulation is described in Section 4. In Section 5, a brief overview of the ocean circulation in the Atlantic-Arctic Ocean is given, together with the observed distribution of the ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr radionuclides. The obtained results from the hindcast and the future simulations are given in Section 6 and 7, respectively, and the report is summarized in Section 7.

3 Model description

The model system applied in this study is the OGCM MICOM (Bleck et al., 1992), fully coupled to a sea-ice module consisting of the Hibler (1979) rheology in the implementation of Harder (1996), and the thermodynamics of Drange and Simonsen (1996).

The model has 23 layers with fixed potential densities, and an uppermost mixed layer (ML) with temporal and spatial varying density. The specified potential densities of the subsurface layers were chosen to ensure a realistic representation of the major water masses in the North Atlantic-Nordic Sea region. The densities of the isopycnic layers (in σ_0 -units) are 24.12, 24.70, 25.28, 25.77, 26.18, 26.52, 26.80, 27.03, 27.22, 27.38, 27.52, 27.63, 27.71, 27.77, 27.82, 27.86, 27.90, 27.94, 27.98, 28.01, 28.04, 28.07 and 28.10. In the horizontal, the model is configured with a local orthogonal grid mesh with one pole over North America and one pole over western part of Asia (Bentsen et al., 1999), yielding a grid-spacing of about 90–120 km in the North Atlantic-Nordic Seas region.

The vertically homogeneous ML utilises the Gaspar (1988) bulk parameterization for the dissipation of turbulent kinetic energy, and has temperature, salinity and layer thickness as the prognostic variables. In the isopycnic layers below the ML, temperature and layer thickness are the prognostic variables, whereas salinity is diagnostically determined by means of the simplified equation of state of (Friedrich and Levitus, 1972). The bathymetry is computed as the arithmetic-mean value based on the ETOPO-5 data base (Data Announcement 88-MGG-02, Digital relief of the Surface of the Earth, NOAA, National Geophysical Data Center, Boulder, Colorado, 1988).

The continuity, momentum and tracer equations are discretised on an Arakawa C-grid

stencil (Arakawa and Lamb, 1977). The diffusive velocities (diffusivities divided by the size of the grid cell) for layer interface diffusion, momentum dissipation, and tracer dispersion are 0.015 m s^{-1} , 0.015 m s^{-1} and 0.005 m s^{-1} , respectively. A flux corrected transport scheme (Zalesak, 1979; Smolarkiewicz and Clark, 1986) is used to advect the model layer thickness and the tracer quantities.

The diapycnal mixing coefficient K_d ($\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is parameterized according to the Gargett (1984) expression $K_d = 3 \times 10^{-7}/N$, where N (s^{-1}) is the Brunt-Väisälä frequency. The numerical implementation of the diapycnal mixing follows the scheme of McDougall and Dewar (1998).

The model was initialized by the January Levitus and Boyer (1994) and Levitus et al. (1994) climatological temperature and salinity fields, respectively, a 2 m thick sea-ice cover based on climatological sea-ice extent, and an ocean at rest. The model was first spin-up for 180 years with monthly-mean atmospheric forcing fields derived from the NCEP/NCAR reanalysis (Kalnay et al., 1996). In this spin-up, both sea surface salinity (SSS) and sea surface temperature (SST) was relaxed towards monthly mean surface climatology. The relaxation was carried out by applying fluxes of heat and salt proportional to the SSS and SST differences between model and climatology, respectively, with an e -folding time scale of 30 days for a ML of 50 m or less, decreasing linearly with thicker ML depths. The spin-up was then continued with daily NCEP/NCAR forcing, repeating the period 1974-1978 twice. Only salinity relaxation was applied in these two integrations, and the deduced salinity adjustment flux was stored from the latter integration to produce seasonal averaged restoring fluxes for salt. The period 1974-1978 was chosen because of the relatively neutral North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO; Hurrell 1995) conditions of these years (see below). Thereafter, for the hindcast simulation, the model was integrated with daily forcing for the period 1948-1999 with no relaxation but with the diagnosed restoring fluxes for salt.

For the simulation of ^{90}Sr originating from accidental releases in the Ob and Yenisey rivers in a future climate, twin-integrations have been conducted. The base-line integration is similar to the hind-cast simulation described above, i.e., a simulation under present climate conditions covering the time period from 1970 to 2000. Here the daily NCEP/NCAR re-analyses (Kalnay et al., 1996) are used. For the global warming scenario, daily atmospheric forcing fields were extracted from a $2\times\text{CO}_2$ simulation performed with the Bergen Climate Model (BCM; Furevik et al. 2002). To ensure that the OGCM is driven by forcing fields consistent with the NCAR/NCEP forcing, the following procedure was adopted: In step one, the mean daily value of all of the atmospheric forcing fields from the last 30 years of the $2\times\text{CO}_2$ simulation was stored. Then the difference between these daily forcing fields and the climatological mean of the same fields from a control integration with BCM was computed. In this way, the obtained product is the daily change in the atmospheric forcing fields caused by increased concentration of atmospheric CO_2 in BCM. Finally, the daily forcing anomalies from the $2\times\text{CO}_2$ BCM simulation were added to the mean of the NCAR/NCEP re-analyses fields for the period 1970-2000.

3.1 The tracer module

The transport and mixing of the radionuclides follow the equation (Bleck et al., 1992)

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial s} C \right) + \underbrace{\nabla_s \cdot (\vec{v} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} C)}_{\text{advection}} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial s} (\dot{s} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} C)}_{\text{mass transfer}} = \underbrace{\nabla_s \cdot \left(\nu \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} \nabla_s C \right)}_{\text{diffusion}} + \underbrace{\delta C}_{\text{source/sink}} - \underbrace{\lambda C}_{\text{decay}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: The time evolution of ^{137}Cs (bars) and ^{90}Sr (line) from (a) the Sellafield release (unit: $10^{12} \text{ Bq y}^{-1}$) and (b) the atmospheric fallout (unit: $\text{Bq m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$) over Denmark. (S. Nilsen, pers. comm., 2001).

Here p is the interface pressure of the isopycnals, C is the concentrations of the tracers, \bar{v} is the isopycnal velocity, s is the vertical coordinate, ν is the diffusive velocity for the tracers, and λ denotes the decay of C . Both ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr are soluble in sea water and can be considered as passive tracers with a half-life of 30.1 and 29 years, respectively.

4 Setup of the radionuclides simulation

4.1 the hindcast simulation

Nuclear bomb testing, the Chernobyl accident and release from the European reprocessing plants Sellafield (UK) and Cap de La Hague (France) are the most important sources for the radionuclides in the North Atlantic-Arctic region (Nies et al., 1998). The time evolution of ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr from the Sellafield release, from the nuclear bomb testing and from the Chernobyl accident in 1986 over Denmark (S. Nilsen, pers. comm., 2001) are shown in Fig. 1. The atmospheric fallout provides the present background concentration of the surface and sub-surface waters in the region, while the Sellafield discharge is one of the major sources of radioactive contamination in the Arctic Ocean since the the 1970s (Strand et al., 1996)). The Sellafield signal has been observed for the last two decades, making model-evaluation of in particular ^{137}Cs distributions possible.

The latitudinal distribution of the atmospheric ^{90}Sr deposition (UNSCEAR 1982, see Fig. 2) makes it feasible to construct the latitudinal distribution of the atmospheric fallout of ^{137}Cs , with the fallout of ^{137}Cs a factor 1.6 higher than that of ^{90}Sr (Strand et al., 1998). Furthermore, Fig. 3 shows the reconstructed time evolution of ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr caused by the river discharges at the mouths of the Ob and Yenisey rivers in the Kara Sea (Dziuba et al., 2002).

A total of seven tracers are included in the simulation: The atmospheric fallout of ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr , the Sellafield discharge of ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr , the ^{90}Sr caused by the discharges from the Ob and Yenisey rivers and ^{137}Cs caused by the Yenisey river discharge only. The Chernobyl accident in 1986, seen as the isolated peak in the atmospheric fallout in Fig. 1b, is not included

Figure 2: The atmospheric deposition of ^{90}Sr (kBq m^{-2}) vs. latitude (UNSCEAR 1982).

in the present analyses due to uncertainties in prescribing the spatial-temporal source function.

The initial fields of all of the radionuclides are set to zero. The simulation starts in 1950 and ends in 1999.

4.2 Simulation on accidental releases

Fig. 4 shows the proposed accidental daily release of ^{90}Sr from the Ob and Yenisey rivers. The maximum accidental releases take place in summer, with the maximum values of 116 Bq m^{-3} for the Ob river and 302 Bq m^{-3} for the Yenisey river. The integration of the accidental release scenarios start from 1970 with zero concentrations in the sea and ends in 2000 with the present-day climate condition, and starts from 2050 with zero concentrations in the sea and ends at 2080 with the $2\times\text{CO}_2$ forcing.

5 Observed distribution of water masses and radionuclides

The Ocean circulation in the region of interest is complex and is characterized by warm and saline surface Atlantic Water (AW) flowing through the Denmark Strait, passing the ridge between Iceland and the Faroes, and entering east of the Faroes (Hansen and Østerhus, 2000). Observational based estimates of the transport of AW through these openings are 1 Sv (Hansen and Østerhus, 2000), 3.3 Sv (Hansen and Østerhus, 2000) and 4.3 Sv (Turrell et al., 2002), respectively ($1 \text{ Sv} = 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). The Atlantic Water continues northward along the Norwegian coast as the Norwegian Atlantic Current (NAC). One branch of the AW enters the Barents Sea (2.3 Sv ; Ingvaldsen et al. 2002), whereas the remaining AW continues to the Fram Strait as the West Spitsbergen Current (WSC). Here a fraction of the AW subducts and enters the Arctic Ocean, whereas the rest recirculates and flows southward.

The mean simulated surface current field from the applied model in the Atlantic-Arctic region is displayed in Fig. 5. The circulation field is, in general, in accordance with observations. The most pronounced exception is the too northerly separation of the Gulf Stream off

Figure 3: (a) The time evolution of ^{137}Cs concentration (Bq m^{-3}) (monthly data from 1958 to 1995) at the mouth of Yenisey river in the Kara Sea caused by the river discharge, and (b) the time evolution of ^{90}Sr concentration (Bq m^{-3}) at the mouth of Yenisey (red line) and Ob rivers (black line) in the Kara Sea caused by the river discharge (monthly data from 1949 to 1993 for Ob river and from 1958 to 1995 for Yenisey data). Data from Dziuba et al. (2002).

Figure 4: Proposed accidental release of ^{90}Sr (Bq m^{-3}) from the Ob river (solid line) and the Yenisey river (dashed line) (Dziuba et al., 2002). The x -axes indicate the time for the simulation with the present day (lower x -axis) and the $2\times\text{CO}_2$ (upper x -axis) climate forcing.

Figure 5: The simulated mean circulation field in the upper 100 m of the water column for the period 1950 to 1999.

the North American coast. This is a classical problem for OGCMs; a properly resolved Gulf Stream requires a horizontal resolution one order of magnitude higher than in the present integration (Bleck et al., 1995).

Furthermore, the general surface ocean circulation in the Arctic Ocean is dominated by the Beaufort Gyre and the Transpolar Drift (TPD). As already stated, volume exchanges between the Arctic Ocean and the North Atlantic takes place via the Barents Sea and through the Fram Strait. The cold and fresh Polar Water leaves the Arctic with the East Greenland Current (EGC) on the western side of the Fram Strait. This water continues southward along the coast of Greenland. Most of the polar water flows through the Denmark Strait and enters the sub-polar gyre. A branch of the cold and fresh Arctic water flows eastward north of the Denmark Strait and is trapped in the cyclonically directed circulation in the Nordic Seas.

The pathway of the soluble radionuclides ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr from Sellafield to the Arctic has been summarized by Kershaw and Baxter (1995) (see Fig. 6): Initially the tracer is carried northward from the Irish Sea as a plume-like structure via the North Channel, and it then flows along the coast of Scotland into the North Sea. The tracer is transported northward before branching off northern Norway: One branch passes eastwards into the Barents Sea; the other passes through the Fram Strait with the WSC. The main surface water return flow occurs with the EGC. In case the tracer is mixed into sub-surface waters, the return flow will also include the Denmark Strait overflow, the overflow across the Iceland-Faroe Ridge and the Faroe-Bank Channel overflow (Hansen and Østerhus, 2000).

Figure 6 also provides estimated transit times for the Sellafield release. It follows that the signal enters the Barents Sea after about 4 years. In the Fram Strait, the transit time is about 5 years for the AW and 6-10 years for the southward flowing Arctic waters. After additional two years, the Sellafield signal passes the Denmark Strait, and continues cyclonically along

Figure 6: Estimated pathway and transit time (yr) of the Sellafield signal, adapted from Dahlgard (1995).

the periphery of the sub-polar gyre. It is further speculated that a part of the signal from the sub-polar gyre re-enters the northward flowing AW after a total transit time of 14-17 years.

6 Results from the hindcast simulation

6.1 ^{137}Cs from atmospheric fallout and the Sellafield release

Before extending northward with the NAC, the simulated Sellafield radionuclides circulate cyclonically in the North Sea (see Figs. 5 and 7a). One branch enters the Barents Sea, and one branch heads towards the Fram Strait following the WSC. The simulated pathway of the Sellafield release to the Barents Sea is in general agreement with observations (Kershaw and Baxter 1995, and Fig. 6). In the Barents Sea, the Sellafield signal spreads towards north-east, and one branch enters the northern Kara Sea. The simulated Sellafield signal has passed the Denmark Strait by the EGC in year 1975 and is found in the Labrador Sea in the early 1980s. It should be noted that the simulated Sellafield signal does not extend eastward of the Kara Sea, instead, the signal propagates westward following the Canadian Archipelago in the 1980s. It is also seen that the surface ^{137}Cs concentration decreases quickly in the late 1990s.

Figures 8 and 9 display the evolution of the vertically integrated inventory of ^{137}Cs and the ratio of the vertically integrated inventory from Sellafield to that from atmospheric fallout, respectively. Generally, the inventory in the central Arctic Ocean is low due to the rather weak intrusion of the radioactive signal from the AW. In the Barents Sea and west of Norway, the Sellafield contribution plays the dominant role in the inventory in the 1970s and 1980s. In the central Nordic Seas, the Sellafield source dominates the inventory from the mid 1980s.

The distribution of the Sellafield signal is closely associated with the simulated circulation field in the region. In Fig. 10, the circulation *anomalies* associated with years with high (1957, 61, 73, 75, 76, 81, 83, 84, 89, 90, 92, 93, 94, 95, 99) and low (1958, 60, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 68, 69, 70, 71, 77, 79, 87, 96) North Atlantic Oscillation index (NAO; Hurrell 1995) are displayed. The high and low NAO anomalies are associated with the most profound atmospheric winter time anomalies in the region (Visbeck et al., 2002), and therefore illustrate the degree of long-term (i.e., multi-annual) variability in the surface circulation field. It should be mentioned that short-term variability occurring on time scales of days to months will far exceed the variability depicted in Fig. 10. The robust long-term changes, however, are expected to follow the changes in Fig. 10.

For high NAO-forcing (i.e., for fairly persistent and strong westerlies in the North Atlantic), there is an enhanced northward transport of water east of the Faroes and southward transport through the Denmark Strait (Fig. 10a). This result is in general accordance with observational based estimates (Nilsen et al., 2003). There are also enhanced surface transports into the Barents Sea and of Arctic waters out of the Arctic Ocean through the Fram Strait. For years with low NAO-forcing, the anomalies oppositely mirror those of the high NAO-forcing closely (Fig. 10a).

The temporal variability of the simulated volume transports over the uppermost 100 m of the water column for some of the major openings in the Nordic Seas-Arctic region is provided in Fig. 11. The trend seen in these panels are in general agreement with the gradually increasing NAO-index over the time period from the early 1960s to the mid 1990s (Hurrell, 1995), and points toward the need for using synoptic rather than climatological forcing fields for tracer simulations.

Figure 7: Simulated surface distribution of ^{137}Cs (Bq m $^{-3}$) in December 1970 to December 1999 caused by the Sellafield release. Concentration scale in (h), with a cut-off value of 1 Bq m $^{-3}$.

Figure 8: Simulated vertically integrated inventory of ^{137}Cs (Bq m^{-2}) in December 1970 to December 1999 caused by the Sellafield release and atmospheric fallout. Inventory scale in (h), with a cut-off value of 2000 Bq m^{-2} .

Figure 9: Simulated ratio of the vertically integrated inventory of the Sellafield release to that of the atmospheric fallout in December 1970 to December 1999. Ratio scale in (h), with a cut-off value of 0.1.

(a) Surface flow anomalies for high NAO

(b) Surface flow anomalies for low NAO

Figure 10: The simulated surface circulation anomalies for high (a) and low (b) NAO indexes.

Figure 11: Simulated time series of the volume transports (in Sv) over the upper 100 m for (a) the northward transport through the Faroe-Shetland Chanel, (b) the northward transport through the Barents Opening, (c) the southward transport through the Fram Strait, and (d) the southward transport through the Denmark Strait. The thick solid lines indicate the averaged surface transport over the period from 1950 to 1999 (2.2 Sv, 1.8 Sv, 2.1 Sv and 2.2 Sv, respectively).

To qualitatively and quantitatively evaluate the simulated transport and mixing of the Sellafield discharge, time series of the observed and simulated surface ^{137}Cs concentration east of Scotland (57.0-57.5°N, 1.5-2.0°W), west of Norway (59-61°N, 3.5-5.0°E) and in the south-western Barents Sea region (71-72°N, 20-30°E) are shown in Fig. 12. Superimposed on the panels, a histogram of the annual mean Sellafield discharge rates are shown.

Clearly, the atmospheric fallout dominates the surface ^{137}Cs distribution in mid 1960s in the three regions. However, from the late 1970s to the late 1980s, the Sellafield discharge heavily dominates the surface concentrations. For the last 5-10 years of the simulation, the surface concentrations of ^{137}Cs are mainly governed by the atmospheric fallout.

The temporal and spatial evolution of the surface ^{137}Cs concentrations are in broad agreement with observations (Fig. 12a, b, c). However, the simulated surface ^{137}Cs concentrations are generally lower than the observed values. For instance, the maximum concentration in the Barents Sea is about 75% of the observed value. This finding, at least up to the Chernobyl accident in 1986, may indicate that the applied model resolution is too coarse, leading to a too violent mixing. It is also likely that reduced diapycnal and isopycnal mixing rates of a factor 2-4 would maintain higher peak tracer concentrations (cfr. Gao et al. 2003a).

Based on the simulated ^{137}Cs concentration fields, the time for the Sellafield release to reach eastern Scotland is 2 years, 4 years for western Norway and 4-5 years for south-western Barents Sea. The transit time is here defined as the difference in time when the maximum concentration occurs in the specific region and when the maximum Sellafield release occurred. The simulated transit times are in accordance with available, observational-based studies (Kershaw and Baxter 1995; Livingston et al. 1984; and Fig. 6).

6.2 ^{90}Sr from the atmospheric fallout, the Sellafield release, the Ob and Yenisey discharges

Figures 13 to 18 show the surface distribution of ^{90}Sr from the atmospheric fallout, the Sellafield release, the Ob and Yenisey rivers, and the ratio of the atmospheric fallout, the Sellafield release, and the Ob and Yenisey discharges to the total surface ^{90}Sr concentration in December of 1955, 1960, 1970, 1980, 1990 and 1999, respectively.

In 1955, high concentrations of ^{90}Sr are found in the Kara Sea with values between several hundred to three thousand Bq m^{-3} close the mouth of the Ob river. The river discharges spread towards the Fram Strait with values up to 60 Bq m^{-3} . Concentrations below 5 Bq m^{-3} are found on the eastern and western sides of the North Atlantic and in the coastal waters off western Norway. The highest concentration of ^{90}Sr is mainly governed by the Ob river release, whereas the low concentration is mainly governed by the atmospheric fallout. The Sellafield release is responsible for the elevated ^{90}Sr concentrations in the Irish Sea and in the Atlantic waters in the North Sea.

In 1960, the Ob river signal dominates the ^{90}Sr distribution in the Kara Sea, over most of the Arctic Ocean, and along the eastern and western coasts of Greenland. Furthermore, a fraction of the ^{90}Sr that is transported by the Eastern Greenland Currents (EGC) is also found north of Iceland. The atmospheric fallout signal dominates over most of the North Atlantic, whereas one branch of the Sellafield signal is about to enter the Barents Sea, whereas another branch heads towards the Fram Strait.

During the 1960s, the ^{90}Sr signal generally weakens compared with the concentration distributions in 1955 and 1960. The Ob river signal still dominates in the Kara Sea, most of the Arctic Ocean and in the region of the EGC, whereas the atmospheric fallout dominates

(a) ^{137}Cs east of Scotland ($57.0\text{-}57.5^\circ\text{N}$, $1.5\text{-}2.0^\circ\text{W}$)

(b) ^{137}Cs west of Norway ($59\text{-}61^\circ\text{N}$, $3.5\text{-}5.0^\circ\text{E}$)

(c) ^{137}Cs in the Barents Sea ($71\text{-}72^\circ\text{N}$, $20\text{-}30^\circ\text{E}$)

Figure 12: Time series of the imposed Sellafield release rates of ($10^{12} \text{ Bq y}^{-1}$; bars), the observed ^{137}Cs surface concentration (Bq m^{-3}) from Kershaw and Baxter (1995) in circles, and the simulated surface concentration for atmospheric fallout (dashed lines) and the sum of the Sellafield release and the atmospheric fallout (solid lines) for East of Scotland (upper row), West of Norway (mid row) and in the South-West Barents Sea region (lower row). Note the different concentration scales on the panels.

Figure 13: Simulated total surface concentration of ^{90}Sr (Bq m^{-3}) in December, 1955 (a), the ratio of atmospheric fallout induced ^{90}Sr to total ^{90}Sr (b), the ratio of Sellafield release induced ^{90}Sr to total ^{90}Sr (c) and the ratio of Ob river discharge induced ^{90}Sr to total ^{90}Sr (d). The concentration and the ratio legends are displayed in (e) and (f) respectively. The cut off value of the ^{90}Sr concentration is 1 Bq m^{-3} .

Figure 14: As Fig. 13, but for year 1960.

Figure 15: As Fig. 13, but for year 1970.

west coast of Norway. The contribution from the Sellafield release is minor and is confined to the Irish Sea.

In 1970, a peak concentration of about 100 Bq m^{-3} is found in the Irish Sea, and this is caused by the Sellafield plant. The total signal of ^{90}Sr is generally weakened in the Arctic-Nordic Seas region. The atmospheric fallout dominates over the Ob river discharge in the Nordic Seas, with the exception of the coastal waters off Norway that is influenced by the Sellafield release.

In the period between 1970 to 1980, the Ob river discharge is the dominant source for ^{90}Sr in the Kara Sea and in the Canadian Basin of the Arctic Ocean. The Yenisey discharge is low, and the effect of this discharge is confined to the Kara Sea. Further south, the Sellafield release is responsible for a major part of the ^{90}Sr in the North Sea, along the coast of Norway, and in the southern Barents Sea. Atmospheric fallout dominates in the northern part of the Atlantic Ocean and in the central and western part of the Nordic Seas.

In the following decade, the atmospheric fallout and the Ob river discharge are about equally important for the ^{90}Sr distribution in the Arctic Ocean. In the Nordic Seas, the distribution of ^{90}Sr is about equally governed by the atmospheric fallout, the Ob river discharge and the Sellafield release.

Towards 1999, the concentration of ^{90}Sr is low (typically below 2 Bq m^{-3}) and atmospheric fallout dominates over the Ob river discharge and the Sellafield release in both the Arctic Ocean and in the Nordic Seas. The Yenisey river signal is mainly confined to the Kara Sea through the simulated period.

The simulated time evolution of ^{90}Sr in the Kara Sea matches the observed concentrations quite well (Fig. 19). It follows that the Ob river discharge dominates the ^{90}Sr concentration before 1970 despite the atmospheric fallout induced ^{90}Sr reaches its peak value in the late 1960s (Fig. 1b). Between mid-1980 and mid-1990, the atmospheric fallout, the Ob river discharge and the Sellafield release are equally important for the concentration of ^{90}Sr . It is also evident that the Yenisey river discharge plays a relatively minor role in the total concentration of ^{90}Sr in the Kara Sea region.

7 Spreading of accidental released ^{90}Sr under present-day and a $2\times\text{CO}_2$ warming scenario

The accidental released ^{90}Sr from the Ob river is shown in Fig. 20 and 21. For both the present-day and the $2\times\text{CO}_2$ warming scenario runs, ^{90}Sr spreads eastwards following the coast of Siberia and thereafter north- and westwards heading towards the Fram Strait. At the Fram Strait, a branch of ^{90}Sr -enriched water flows southward along the coast off Greenland, whereas another branch enters the Arctic Ocean north of Greenland and the Canadian Archipelago.

The difference between the present-day and the $2\times\text{CO}_2$ warming scenario runs are illustrated by comparing panel (e) and (f) in Fig. 21. It follows that, in general, the transport is accelerated in the $2\times\text{CO}_2$ warming scenario run. Whereas the difference between the two integrations is small in the Nordic Seas, substantial differences are evident in the Arctic Ocean. In the $2\times\text{CO}_2$ warming scenario run, ^{90}Sr -enriched water enters the basin along the coasts of Siberia and Greenland/the Canadian Archipelago. This finding indicates that the high latitude circulation pattern is quite different between the two forcing situations.

In a similar way, the accidental released ^{90}Sr from the Yenisey river is shown in Fig. 22 and 23. The conclusion for the Yenisey discharge follows that of the Ob discharge: The

Figure 16: As Fig. 15, but for year 1980.

Figure 17: As Fig. 16, but for year 1990.

Figure 18: As Fig. 16, but for year 1999.

Figure 19: Time evolution of surface concentration of ^{90}Sr (Bq m^{-3}) in the Kara Sea. The red line represents the time evolutions of the total ^{90}Sr concentration, the black line the Ob river induced ^{90}Sr , the green line the atmospheric fallout induced ^{90}Sr , the dashed line the Yenisey river induced ^{90}Sr , and the blue line the Sellafield release induced ^{90}Sr . The filled red circles are observed concentration from Strand et al. (1998). Note the logarithm scale used for the concentrations.

transport is quickest in the $2 \times \text{CO}_2$ warming scenario run, and the transport into the Arctic Ocean is strongest in the $2 \times \text{CO}_2$ warming scenario run.

For both the Ob and Yenisey releases, the peak value of surface ^{90}Sr concentration moves out of the Kara Sea in the $2 \times \text{CO}_2$ warming scenario run, instead of being blocked in the Kara Sea under the present-day forcing. Consequently, the vulnerable regions for a potential accidental release of ^{90}Sr in the Ob and Yenisey rivers in a future climate are along the eastern coast of Greenland and the coast of the Siberia.

The reason for the obtained differences in the spatial distribution of the Ob and Yenisey releases of ^{90}Sr follows from Fig. 24. It is clear that the surface circulation is more energetic in the global warming scenario, leading to an intensified North Atlantic Drift, a stronger EGC, and to a shift in the circulation pattern in the Arctic Ocean. In fact, the difference between the present-day and the global warming simulations shown in Fig. 24 exceeds the difference between years with high and low NAO forcing at the present-day climate (Fig. 10.).

The long-term concentration and surface flow characteristics are provided in Figs. 25 to 28. An illustration of the effect of the obtained changes in the surface circulation (Fig. 28) is given by panels (a) and (b) in Fig. 26. It follows that more of the released ^{90}Sr is confined to the Nordic Seas/Arctic Ocean in the global warming run, and that the distribution is different in the Arctic Ocean with a change in the location of the ^{90}Sr -enriched waters from the Kara Sea region at the present-day forcing to the coastal, non-European sector in the global warming run. It should be stressed that although large local differences in the spatial distribution of the tracers, the displayed concentration levels are very low.

Figure 20: Spreading of accidental released ^{90}Sr (Bq m^{-3}) from Ob river under present climate condition (left panels) and under the global warming scenario (double CO_2 ; right panels). The concentration scale is the same as Fig. 13e.

Figure 21: Spreading of accidental released ^{90}Sr (Bq m^{-3}) from Ob river under present climate condition (left panels) and under the global warming scenario (double CO_2 ; right panels). The concentration scale is the same as Fig. 13e.

Figure 22: Spreading of accidental released ^{90}Sr (Bq m^{-3}) from Yenisey river under present climate condition (left panels) and under the global warming scenario (double CO_2 ; right panels). The concentration scale is the same as Fig. 13e.

Figure 23: Spreading of accidental released ^{90}Sr (Bq m^{-3}) from Yenisey river under present climate condition (left panels) and under the global warming scenario (double CO_2 ; right panels). The concentration scale is the same as Fig. 13e.

(a) Surface flow between 1971 and 1975

(b) Surface flow between 2051 and 2055

(c) Surface flow anomalies under global warming

Figure 24: The simulated surface circulation between 1971 and 1975 (a), between 2051 and 2055 under the global warming scenario (b) and the difference (present-day minus global warming) between the two periods (c).

(a) December 1980

(b) December 2060

(c) December 1980

(d) December 2060

⁹⁰Sr (Bq m⁻³)

(e) conc.scale for (a,b)

⁹⁰Sr (Bq m⁻³)

(f) conc.scale for (c,d)

Figure 25: Spreading of accidental released ⁹⁰Sr (Bq m⁻³) from the Ob river (a,b) and from the Yenisey river (c,d) under present climate condition (a,c) and under the global warming scenario (double CO₂; (b,d)). The concentration scales are showed in (e,f) for the Ob and Yenisey rives, respectively.

Figure 26: Spreading of accidental released ^{90}Sr (Bq m^{-3}) from the Ob river (a,b) and from the Yenisey river (c,d) under present climate condition (a,c) and under the global warming scenario (double CO_2 ; (b,d)). The concentration scales are showed in (e,f) for the Ob and Yenisey rives, respectively.

(a) December 2000

(b) December 2080

(c) December 2000

(d) December 2080

⁹⁰Sr (Bq m⁻³)

(e) conc.scale for (a,b)

⁹⁰Sr (Bq m⁻³)

(f) conc.scale for (c,d)

Figure 27: Spreading of accidental released ⁹⁰Sr (Bq m⁻³) from the Ob river (a,b) and from the Yenisey river (c,d) under present climate condition (a,c) and under the global warming scenario (double CO₂; (b,d)). The concentration scales are showed in (e,f) for the Ob and Yenisey rivers, respectively.

(a) Surface flow between 1970 and 2000

(b) Surface flow between 2050 and 2080

(c) Surface flow anomalies under global warming

Figure 28: The simulated surface circulation between 1970 and 2000 (a), between 2050 and 2080 under the global warming scenario (b) and the difference (present-day minus global warming) between the two periods (c).

8 Discussion and conclusion

The quality or realism of simulated tracer distributions is by necessity constrained by the simulated water mass transport and transformation rates. The classical way to validate an OGCM is to perform some base-line integrations, and thereafter compare the simulated fields (temperature, salinity, velocity, and derived parameters thereof) with observations. Based on this comparison, model parameters can be tuned, parameterization schemes changed or the numerics improved. In addition, inherent model deficiencies can be uncovered.

Unfortunately, the temporal-spatial distribution of hydrodynamic and dynamic *in situ* ocean observations are sparse. In addition, apparently realistic simulated hydrography can lead to erroneous current fields as demonstrated by e.g. Toggweiler et al. (1989). For this reason, validation of OGCMs based on well-documented tracer distributions with well-defined source functions (e.g. chlorofluorocarbons and natural and bomb-produced radiocarbon), in addition to the conventional hydrographic and transport validations, represent a powerful and cost-efficient OGCM validation strategy (England and Holloway, 1998; England and Maier-Reimer, 2001).

A well-tested and validated numerical model system can be used to provide guidance of the short-term (days) to long-term (decadal) transport and spreading of trace compounds for prescribed source functions. This can be done by performing a series of integrations with the OGCM forced with atmospheric fields provided by an atmospheric forecast system with predictable skill of typically 4-6 days, by forcing a series of OGCM simulations with combinations of observed reanalyses fields available for the last 50 years (e.g. from the NCAR/NCEP re-analyses project, Kalnay et al. 1996) or, for a global warming scenario, by adopting forcing fields from a fully coupled climate model. For all types of experiments, the ensemble mean pathway and concentration level, together with statistics describing the spreading of the ensemble members, yield information about the likely spatial-temporal evolution of the tracers. These results are valuable as input for optimizing the observational strategy and to assess transit times and possible transport routes of the tracers.

In addition, the circulation field and water mass transformation rates from an OGCM can be used to identify possible source locations of various trace compounds based on isolated observations. The use of such an inverse modeling approach is a powerful tool for guiding an observational network to monitor the origin and the spatial-temporal evolution of the tracers.

In the model study of Nies et al. (1998), monthly mean climatological forcing fields were used, yielding a simulated transport time from Sellafield to the Barents Sea of 6 years. In the simulation presented here, the corresponding time is 4-5 years, or approximately the transit time based on observations. The difference highlights the importance of using the more energetic synoptic forcing fields to drive the model. In addition, synoptic forcing fields will, in general, result in year-to-year variations in the simulated current fields (Figs. 10 and 11), and thereby influence the simulated speed and pathway of the tracers. For instance, the spreading of the Sellafield signal in the Arctic Ocean in this study is quite different from that in Nies et al. (1998). In the latter study, peak values of the Sellafield signal were obtained in 1985 and 1990 at the North Pole, whereas mainly found on the Atlantic side of the Pole in this study (Fig. 7). It is hard to assess which model realisation is the most realistic. It is well known, however, that the sea ice and surface water circulation in the Arctic Ocean are highly determined by the natural variability modes of the atmospheric circulation, notably the NAO and the closely associated Arctic Oscillation (AO; Mysak 2001). It is therefore of particular importance to use realistic atmospheric forcing fields when simulating transport and mixing

of tracers in the Arctic Ocean.

The synoptic-forced integration presented here shows some of the features that can be deduced from an OGCM tracer simulation. It is, as an example, interesting to note that in the AW off the coast of Norway, the atmospheric fallout of ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr dominates over the Sellafield release from the early 1990s and onwards (see Fig. 9f and g). The degree of realism of this finding highly depends on the quality of the simulated transport and mixing processes, and the representativeness of the applied time history of the Sellafield release and the atmospheric fallout. It is also interesting to note how the radionuclides signal first builds up and thereafter diminishes in the Nordic Seas-Arctic Ocean region. This shift is most clearly seen in the 1980s when a substantial fraction of the radionuclides is transported southward across the Greenland-Scotland Ridge, before continuing southward in the Atlantic Ocean as a part of the geostrophically-controlled Deep Western Boundary Current off the coast North America (particularly Figs. 8e-g).

The simulated time evolution of ^{90}Sr in the Kara Sea matches the observed concentrations quite well (Fig. 19). It follows that the Ob river discharge dominates the ^{90}Sr concentration before 1970 despite the atmospheric fallout induced ^{90}Sr reaches its peak value in the late 1960s (Fig. 1b). Between mid-1980 and mid-1990, the atmospheric fallout, the Ob river discharge and the Sellafield release are equally important for the concentration of ^{90}Sr . It is also evident that the Yenisey river discharge plays a relatively minor role in the total concentration of ^{90}Sr in the Kara Sea region.

It is also worth mentioned that for the Arctic Ocean ^{90}Sr , the Ob river discharge highly dominates in the 1950s and 1960s (Figs. 13–14), and that the Ob river is equally or more important than the atmospheric fallout in the 1970s and 1980s (Figs. 15–16). In the Arctic, the contribution from the Sellafield ^{90}Sr release is very small throughout the integration (Figs. 13–18).

The difference between the present-day and the $2\times\text{CO}_2$ warming scenario runs for the accidental releases of ^{90}Sr in the Ob and Yenisey rivers are illustrated by comparing panels (e) and (f) in Fig. 21, and panels (a) and (b) in Fig. 26. It follows that, in general, the transport is accelerated in the $2\times\text{CO}_2$ warming scenario run and more of the released ^{90}Sr is confined to the Arctic Ocean in the global warming run, particularly in the near coastal, non-European part of the Arctic Ocean. It shows that a global warming scenario may change the surface circulation more than the changes between persistent low and high NAO forcing in the region.

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References

- Arakawa, A., Lamb, V., 1977. Computational design of the basic processes of the UCLA General Circulation Model. *Methods Comput. Phys.* 17, 174–265.
- Bentsen, M., Evensen, G., Drange, H., Jenkins, A. D., 1999. Coordinate Transformation on a Sphere Using Conformal Mapping. *Mon. Wea. Rev.* 127, 2733–2740.
- Bleck, R., Dean, S., Keefe, M. O., Sawdey, A., 1995. A Comparison of Data-Parallel and Message-Passing Versions of the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model. *Parallel Computing* 21, 1695–1720.
- Bleck, R., Rooth, C., Hu, D., Smith, L. T., 1992. Salinity-driven thermohaline transients in a wind- and thermohaline-forced isopycnic coordinate model of the North Atlantic. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.* 22, 1486–1515.
- Dahlgaard, H., 1995. Transfer of European Coastal Pollution to the Arctic: Radioactive Tracers. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 31, 3–7.
- Drange, H., Simonsen, K., 1996. Formulation of air-sea fluxes in the ESOP2 version of MICOM. Tech. Rep. 125, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Edv. Griegsv. 3A, N-5059 Solheimsviken, Norway.
- Dziuba, N., Koshebutsky, K., Maderich, V., Zheleznyak, M., 2002. WP9 Simulation results using the GSM River model realistic run 1949-1995. Tech. rep., Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Bergen, Norway.
- England, M., Holloway, G., 1998. Simulations of CFC content and water mass age in the deep North Atlantic. *J. Geophys. Res.* 103 (C8), 15885–15901.
- England, M., Maier-Reimer, E., 2001. Using Chemical Tracers to Assess Ocean Models. *Rev. of Geophys.* 39 (1), 29–70.
- Friedrich, H., Levitus, S., 1972. An approximation to the equation of state for sea water, suitable for numerical ocean models. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.* 2, 514–517.
- Furevik, T., Bentsen, M., Drange, H., Kindem, I., Kvamstø, N., Sorteberg, A., 2002. Description and validation of the Bergen Climate Model: ARPEGE coupled with MICOM. *Clim. Dyn.* In press.
- Gao, Y., Drange, H., Bension, M., 2003a. Effects of diapycnal and isopycnal mixing on the ventilation of CFCs in the North Atlantic in an isopycnic coordinate OGCM. *Tellus* 55B (3), 837–854.
- Gao, Y., Drange, H., Bension, M., Johannessen, O. M., 2003b. Simulating transport of non-Chernobyl ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr in the North Atlantic-Arctic region. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* In press.
- Gargett, A., 1984. Vertical eddy in the ocean interior. *J. Marine. Res.* 42 (2), 359–393.
- Gaspar, P., 1988. Modeling the seasonal cycle of the upper ocean. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.* 18, 161–180.
- Gerland, S., Lind, B., Dowdall, M., Karcher, M., Kolstad, A. K., 2003. ^{99}Tc in seawater in the West Spitsbergen Current and adjacent areas. *J. Environ. Radioactivity* In press.
- Hansen, B., Østerhus, S., 2000. North Atlantic-Nordic Seas exchanges. *Prog. Oceanogr.* 45 (2), 109–208.
- Harder, M., Jan 1996. Dynamik, Rauigkeit und Alter des Meereises in der Arktis. Ph.D. thesis, Alfred-Wegener-Institut für Polar- und Meeresforschung, Bremerhaven, Germany.
- Hibler, W., 1979. A dynamic thermodynamic sea ice model. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.* 9, 815–846.
- Hurrell, W., 1995. Decadal trends in the north atlantic oscillation: Regional temperatures and precipitation. *Science* 269, 676–679.
- Ingvaldsen, R., Loeng, H., Asplin, L., 2002. Variability in the Atlantic inflow to the Barents Sea based on a one-year time series from moored current meters. *Continental Shelf Research* 22, 505–519.

- Kalnay, E., et al., 1996. The NCEP/NCAR 40-Year Reanalysis Project. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.* 77 (3), 437–471.
- Kershaw, P., Baxter, A., 1995. The transfer of reprocessing wastes from north-west Europe to the Arctic. *Deep Sea Res.* 42, 1413–1448.
- Levitus, S., Boyer, T. P., 1994. *World Ocean Atlas 1994 Volume 4: Temperature*. NOAA Atlas NESDIS 4. Washington, D.C., USA.
- Levitus, S., Burgett, R., Boyer, T. P., 1994. *World Ocean Atlas 1994 Volume 3: Salinity*. NOAA Atlas NESDIS 3. Washington, D.C., USA.
- Livingston, H., Kupferman, S., Bowen, V., Moore, R., 1984. Vertical profile of artificial radionuclide concentrations in the central Arctic Ocean. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 48, 2195–2203.
- McDougall, T., Dewar, W., 1998. Vertical mixing, cabbeling and thermobaricity in layered models. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.* , 1458–1480.
- Mysak, L. A., 2001. Patterns of Arctic Circulation. *Science* 293, 1269–1270.
- Nies, H., Harms, H., Karcher, M., Dethleff, D., Bahe, C., Kuhlmann, G., Oberhuber, J., Backhaus, J., Kleine, E., Loewe, P., Matishov, D., Stepanov, A., Vasiliev, O., 1998. Anthropogenic Radioactivity in the Nordic Seas and the Arctic Ocean - Results of a Joint Project. *Deutsche Hydrographische Zeitschrift* 50 (4), 313–343.
- Nilsen, J. E. Ø., Gao, Y., Drange, H., Furevik, T., Bentsen, M., 2003. Simulated North Atlantic–Nordic Seas water mass exchanges in an isopycnic coordinate OGCM. *Geophys. Res. Letters* 30 (10), 1536, doi:10.1029/2002GL016597.
- Smolarkiewicz, P. K., Clark, T. L., 1986. The multidimensional positive definite advection transport algorithm: Further development and applications. *J. Comp. Phys.* 67, 396–438.
- Strand, P., Aarkrog, A., Bewers, J., Tsaturov, Z., Magnusson, S., 1996. Radioactive Contamination of the Arctic Marine Environment. In: *Radionuclides in the Oceans - Inputs and Inventories*. Inst. de Protection et de Surete Nucleaire, France, pp. 95–119.
- Strand, P., Balonov, M., Aarkrog, A., Bewers, M. J., Howard, B., Salo, A., Tsaturov, Y. S., 1998. Radioactivity. In: *AMAP (Ed.), AMAP assessment report: Arctic pollution issues*. Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP), Oslo, Norway, p. 859.
- Toggweiler, J., Dixon, K., Bryan, K., 1989. Simulations of radiocarbon in a coarse-resolution world ocean model, 1, Steady state prebomb distributions. *J. Geophys. Res.* 94, 8217–8242.
- Tsumune, D., Aoyama, M., Hirose, K., 2003. Numerical simulation of ^{137}Cs and $^{239,240}\text{Pu}$ concentration by an ocean general circulation model. *J. Environ. Radioactivity* In press.
- Turrell, W. R., Hansen, B., Hughes, S., Østerhus, S., 2002. Hydrographic variability during the decade of the 1990s in the Northeast Atlantic and southern Norwegian Sea. In: *ICES Symposium on Hydrobiological Variability in the ICES Area, 1990-99*. ICES Mar. Sci. Symp., ICES.
- UNSCEAR, 1982. *Ionizing Radiation: Sources and Biological Effects*. In: *UNSCEAR 1982 Report to the General Assembly with Scientific Annexes*. United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation, United Nations, New York.
- Visbeck, M., Chassignet, R., Delworth, T., Dickson, B., Krahnemann, G., 2002. The Ocean's Response to North Atlantic Oscillation Variability. In: *Hurrell, J., Kushnir, Y., Ottersen, G., Visbeck, M. (Eds.), The North Atlantic Oscillation*. AGU monograph, in press.
- Zalesak, S., 1979. Fully multidimensional flux-corrected transport algorithms for fluids. *J. Comp. Physics* 31, 335–362.